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Research Article

“COMPARISON OF OUTCOME OF LAPAROENDOSCOPIC SINGLE SITE VERSUS MULTIPORT LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY”

Dr. Hafiz Muhammad Ejaz¹, Dr. Rana Zahid Javed², Dr. Arslan Mir³

¹Consultant Surgeon in Tehsil Headquarter Hospital, Muridkey, Sheikhpura,
Email:ejaz@doctor.com.

²Medical Officer in Rural Health Centre Matotli Shujjabad Multan Punjab,
Email:zahidjaved2000@gmail.com.

³Fatima Memorial Hospital College of Medicine & Dentistry, Lahore,
Email:arslanmir66@gmail.com.

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Abstract:

Introduction: Cholecystectomy is one of the most commonly performed abdominal surgical procedures that are performed laparoscopically. Laparoscopic techniques are rapidly evolving and trends towards a more minimally invasive approach have led to the introduction of single incision. Laparoscopic single-site cholecystectomy has increased in popularity due to its potential cosmetic benefits and faster recovery. It is predicted that this technique may become a standard approach to cholecystectomy in near future.

Methodology: Study Design: Randomized control trial

Setting: This study were done at surgical floor of Jinnah hospital Lahore

Study Duration: 6 months after approval of my synopsis [August 3, 2015-February 2, 2016]

Results: The mean age of patients in group A was 49.99 ± 13.12 years and in group B was 51.64 ± 13.68 years. In group A, there were 47 (52.8%) males and 42 (47.2%) females whereas in group B, there were 45 (50.6%) males and 44 (49.4%) females. The mean duration of surgery in group A was 65.73 ± 13.48 minutes and in group B it was 50.61 ± 9.38 minutes, p -value < 0.001 . The mean stay of patients in the hospital was 1.11 ± 0.32 days for group A and 1.91 ± 0.87 for group B, p -value < 0.001 .

KEYWORDS: Gall stone, Cholecystectomy, laparoscopy, Single site, Multiport, wound infection, pain

Corresponding author:

Dr. Hafiz Muhammad Ejaz,

Consultant Surgeon in Tehsil Headquarter Hospital,
Muridkey, Sheikhpura, Email:ejaz@doctor.com.

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INTRODUCTION:

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is a technique in which gallbladder is removed with instruments placed into small incisions in the abdomen.⁴ Cholecystectomy is the most common major abdominal procedure performed worldwide.² Multiport laparoscopy (with three or more ports) remains the 'gold standard' for Cholecystectomy⁵ but minimally invasive techniques have become an integral part of general surgery, with recent investigation into single-incision laparoscopic cholecystectomy (SILC).^{6, 7} Laparoendoscopic single-site cholecystectomy (LESSC) has increased in popularity due to its potential cosmetic benefits and faster recovery. It is predicted that this technique may become a standard approach to cholecystectomy.^{8, 9} Pan MX et al reported mean pain (VAS) was same in both groups at day 1 i.e. mean pain in laparoendoscopic single-site Cholecystectomy (LESSC) Group was 1.2 ± 0.4 and in multiport laparoscopic Cholecystectomy (MPLC) mean pain was 1.3 ± 1.2 , p-value = 0.2042.¹⁰ The hospital stay was also similar in both groups, i.e. mean hospital stay was 1.4 ± 0.2 days in LESSC group and mean hospital stay in MPLC group was 1.4 ± 0.7 days, p-value > 0.05.¹⁰

While another study reported higher pain at day one was 3 (2-5) in multiport laparoscopic Cholecystectomy and 1 (0-4) in Laparoendoscopic single-site Cholecystectomy Group, p-value < 0.001.⁵ They also reported higher hospital stay in MPLC group i.e. 1(0-5) as compared to LESSC group i.e. 0 (0-2), p-value = 0.014.⁵ That is inconsistent with above cited study.¹⁰

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design: Randomized control trial

Setting: This study were done at surgical floor of Jinnah hospital Lahore.

Study Duration: 6 months after approval of my synopsis [August 3, 2015-February 2, 2016]

Data Collection:

After approval of synopsis from hospital ethical committee 178 patients were enrolled meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients were divided randomly using simple random technique (lottery method). In Group - A patients were treated with Laparoendoscopic single site and in Group-B patients were treated with multiport laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. Patient's data regarding operation time, postoperative pain and at day 1, duration of hospital and infection at day 7 and one month [according to operational definition] were recorded on attached proforma by researcher himself. All the collected data were entered and analyzed in SPSS version 20.

RESULTS:

The mean age of patients in group A was 49.99 ± 13.12 years and in group B was 51.64 ± 13.68 years. In group A, there were 47 (52.8%) males and 42 (47.2%) females whereas in group B, there were 45 (50.6%) males and 44 (49.4%) females. The mean duration of surgery in group A was 65.73 ± 13.48 minutes and in group B it was 50.61 ± 9.38 minutes, p-value < 0.001. The mean stay of patients in the hospital was 1.11 ± 0.32 days for group A and 1.91 ± 0.87 for group B, p-value < 0.001. The pain score (VAS) on 1st postoperative day was 1.67 ± 0.65 in group A and 3.42 ± 0.77 in group B, p-value < 0.001. At 7th day, the wound infection was present in 15 (16.9%) patients in group A and only 5 (5.6%) patients in group B. At 30th day, the wound infection was present in 9 (10.1%) patients in group A and only 2 (2.2%) patients in group B. The wound infection on 7th and 30th postoperative day was significantly lesser in group B (p-value < 0.05).

TABLE-1: COMPARISON OF AGE (YEARS) IN BOTH STUDY GROUPS

	STUDY GROUPS	
	Group-A	Group-B
N	89	89
Mean	49.99	51.64
Std. Deviation	13.12	13.68
Minimum	18	20
Maximum	80	79
p-value	0.412	

TABLE-2: COMPARISON OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN BOTH STUDY GROUPS

		Study groups		Total
		Group-A	Group-B	
Diabetes	Yes	34	32	66
		38.2%	36.0%	37.1%
	No	55	57	112
		61.8%	64.0%	62.9%
Total		89	89	178
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

p-value = 0.75

TABLE-3: COMPARISON OF DURATION OF PAIN (AT DAY 1) IN BOTH STUDY GROUPS WHEN STRATIFIED FOR AGE (YEARS), GENDER AND DIABETES

		Study groups	N	Mean	S.D	p-value
Age groups	18-45	Group-A	28	1.71	0.71	<0.001
		Group-B	37	3.27	0.73	
	46-80	Group-A	61	1.65	0.62	<0.001
		Group-B	52	3.51	0.77	
Gender	Male	Group-A	45	1.64	0.64	< 0.001
		Group-B	47	3.44	0.77	
	Female	Group-A	44	1.70	0.66	< 0.001
		Group-B	42	3.38	0.76	
Diabetes	Yes	Group-A	32	1.65	0.60	< 0.001
		Group-B	34	3.38	0.81	
	No	Group-A	57	1.68	0.68	< 0.001
		Group-B	55	3.43	0.73	

TABLE-4: COMPARISON OF WOUND INFECTION (At 7th Day) IN BOTH STUDY GROUPS WHEN STRATIFIED FOR AGE

Age groups			Study groups		p-value
			Group-A	Group-B	
18-45	Wound infection (day 7)	Yes	6	0	0.028
			16.2%	.0%	
		No	31	28	
			83.8%	100.0%	
46-80	Wound infection (day 7)	Yes	9	5	0.119
			17.3%	8.2%	
		No	43	56	
			82.7%	91.8%	

DISCUSSION:

Gallstone disease is a common and costly disease. Study by Shaffer EA. in 2005 published different epidemiological perspectives of this disease. They reported that in developed countries, at least 10% of white adults harbor cholesterol gallstones; women have twice the risk, and age further increases the prevalence in both sexes. Gallstones reach epidemic proportions in the North and South American Indian populations, accompanied by an increased risk for gallbladder cancer. In contrast, the rate in sub-Saharan Africa and Asia is quite low. They also claimed obesity being most prominent risk factor of gallstone disease. They reported that obesity is a major risk factor, that likely relates to insulin resistance (the metabolic syndrome). Evolution and circumstance in American Indians may have ironically selected those with "thrifty" genes that conserve energy. Our abundant access to food places us at the increased risk of obesity and cholelithiasis. The general rise in obesity in many countries raises the specter of heightened disease, best identified by epidemiologic studies. 53

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is the gold-standard for the treatment of gallbladder stone disease. In recent years laparoendoscopic single site surgery (LESS) has gained greater interest and diffusion for the treatment of gallstones and also in bariatric and colonic surgery. However, in Pakistan, no randomized controlled trials are present in the literature that confirms the clinical advantages of LESS compared with the classic laparoscopic procedures. For this reason, we present the preliminary results of this study regarding the feasibility and safety of LESS cholecystectomy versus classic laparoscopic technique. 81

In our study the mean age of patients in group A was 49.99 ± 13.12 years and in group B was 51.64 ± 13.68 years. The mean duration of surgery in group A was 65.73 ± 13.48 minutes and in group B it was 50.61 ± 9.38 minutes. There was a significantly less duration of surgery with group B (p -value < 0.001). Furthermore, the mean stay of patients in the hospital was 1.91 ± 0.87 days for group B and 1.11 ± 0.32 for group A. The mean duration of stay was significantly lesser in group A (p -value < 0.001).

Hernandez JM. Et al. conducted a study in 2009 to evaluate the first 100 patients undergoing LESS cholecystectomy. In their study one hundred patients with a median age of 44 years underwent LESS cholecystectomy; 30 patients with a median age of 46 years underwent conventional cholecystectomy over the same time period. Median operative time (70 vs 66 minutes, $P = 0.67$, Mann-Whitney) and hospital length of stay (1 vs 1 day, $P = 0.81$, Mann-Whitney) were not different for patients undergoing LESS or multi-incision cholecystectomies, respectively. 82

Another study by Hodgett SE. et al. compared twenty-nine patients of median age 50 years undergoing LESS cholecystectomy from November 2007 until May 2008 to 29 patients, median age 48 years, undergoing standard multiport, multiple-incision laparoscopic cholecystectomy over the same time period. Median operative time for patients undergoing LESS cholecystectomy was 72 min and was not different from that of patients undergoing multiport, multi-incision laparoscopic cholecystectomy ($p = 0.81$). Median length of hospital stay was 1.0 day for patients undergoing LESS cholecystectomy and was not different from patients undergoing standard laparoscopic cholecystectomy ($p = 0.46$). 83 We reported a quite contrasting result to both these studies

where the mean differences of hospital stay as well as operative time were significantly lower in group B.

Apra G. in 2011 studied the results of LESS cholecystectomy versus classic laparoscopic technique. Similar to our results, Apra also reported No differences were registered between the two groups about gender and age. Mean operative time was significantly longer in LESS procedures (41.3 ± 12.0 versus 35.6 ± 5.8 ; $P = 0.04$). Abdominal postoperative pain was similar in LC and LESS cholecystectomy. Wound satisfaction score showed statistically significant differences between the two groups: in LESS group, patients were more satisfied with the presence of a small umbilical medication ($P < 0.05$). All these results are similar to our findings. 81

In our study also, the average pain score (VAS) on 1st postoperative day was 3.42 ± 0.77 in group B and 1.67 ± 0.65 in group A. The mean pain score (VAS) on 1st postoperative day was significantly lesser in group A ($p\text{-value} < 0.001$). At 7th day, the wound infection was present in 15 (16.9%) patients in group A and only 5 (5.6%) patients in group B. The wound infection on 7th postoperative day was significantly lesser in group B ($p\text{-value} < 0.018$). At 30th day, the wound infection was present in 9 (10.1%) patients in group A and only 2 (2.2%) patients in group B. The wound infection on 7th postoperative day was significantly lesser in group B ($p\text{-value} < 0.029$).

Bucher P. compared conventional laparoscopic (CL) with LESS cholecystectomy, with short-term clinical results as the main outcomes. In their study a randomized trial of CL and LESS cholecystectomies involving 150 patients was undertaken. Follow-up was for 1 month after surgery. Operating times and complications were similar in the two groups. However, better pain profiles and lower analgesia requirements were recorded in the LESS group ($P < 0.001$). QoL, body image and scar scale results were also better ($P < 0.001$). Operative costs were higher for LESS procedures ($P < 0.001$), although median time to return to work was shorter ($P = 0.003$). 5 All these results confirm the main findings as well as the hypothesized objective of our study.

In the light of our study, and discussion with available literature which mostly agrees that LESS cholecystectomy was technically feasible, safe, and represents a reproducible alternative to standard laparoscopic cholecystectomy. 84, 85 it can be deduced that LESS is an alternative to conventional laparoscopic cholecystectomy associated with better cosmetics, body image, quality of life and an improved postoperative pain profile. More studies at local level

may further broaden our vision and understanding in this regard.

CONCLUSION:

Through this study we conclude that there was less mean operation time, wound infection at 7th and 30th day multiport site as compared to single site Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. But mean hospital stay and mean Pain Score was less in Laparoendoscopic single when compare to multiport site. In future using Laparoendoscopic single site procedure we can achieve better hospital outcome and can minimize hospital and patient's burden.

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